

Muhtarogullari, A. (2022). Femicide and child marriages in Turkey. *Actual Issues of Modern Science. European Scientific e-Journal*, 22, 94-109. Ostrava: Tuculart Edition, European Institute for Innovation Development.

DOI: 10.47451/soc2022-09-01

The paper will be published in Crossref, ICI Copernicus, Academic Resource Index ResearchBib, J-Gate, ISI International Scientific Indexing, Zenodo, OpenAIRE, BASE, LORY, LUASA, ADL, eLibrary, and WebArchive databases.

Ayşe Muhtarogullari, Assistant Professor, Department of Turkish Psychology, Humanities Faculty, Girne American University, Karmi Campus, Karaoglanoglu, Kyrenia/TRNC, Cyprus.
ORCID 0000-0003-3639-9167.

Femicide and child marriages in Turkey

Abstract: In Turkey, each day women killed because of the domestic violence and also families forced their children to marry before 18s. The legal age of marriage is 18, but also children can marry at the age of 17 and 16 with the permission of family and courts. (Unicef Türkiye). In addition, in Turkey both femicide and early child marriages are connected to each other. Both of them are results of the social biases, which are prejudices, stereotype, and the gender discrimination or the gender inequality. Because of the illiteracy, economic difficulties, education system, and political or government policies, Turkey fights with gender discrimination and early child marriages. The purpose of the study is to analyse the femicide and child marriage cases in Turkey by using the statistical sources to show that femicide and child marriages are one of the big problems of Turkey. The tasks of the study are to finish with the reasons of femicide and child marriages, and offer some solutions to those problems.

Keywords: femicide, child, marriages, Turkey, biases, stereotypes, prejudices, education.

Introduction

Nature-nurture debate is based on political and academic discourses, and it does not have relation with man-made discourses, social-cultural ideologies (Burr, 2002:31). Because of this debate, unfortunately, in this developed century, sex or sexuality is one of the big problems around the world. Still, most of the government policies, academicians, books, articles, and etc. discuss the differences between men and women and relate it with the idea of nature-nurture debate. Even, they talk about the gender discrimination and early child marriages. Both of those problems are the results of the ideological ideas of society, in short, the constructed ideas of people. According to Ann Oakley (1972) sex as a word denotes the biological differences such as male and female, but on the other side gender is related with society such as masculine and feminine. Because of the cultural ideologies or gender inequalities, society and family's pressure early marriages especially among girls (Dağ et al., 2021:549).

In Turkey, each day women killed because of the domestic violence and also families forced their children to marry before 18s. The legal age of marriage is 18, but also children can marry at the age of 17 and 16 with the permission of family and courts. (Unicef Türkiye). In addition, in Turkey both femicide and early child marriages are connected to each other. Both of them are results of the social biases, which are prejudices, stereotype, and the gender discrimination or the

gender inequality. According to Unicef Türkiye “gender inequality that reinforces stereotypical roles for girls and curtails their education, compromises their health, and exposes them to the risk of violence and poverty.” Because of the illiteracy, economic difficulties, education system, and political or government policies Turkey fight with gender discrimination and early child marriages. Especially, the killing of women and girls’ marriages before 18s. Femicide is known as a kind of terror against female such as sexual, physical and verbal. At the end of this terrorism female are murdered by male that we call femicide (*Kouta et al., 2017:1*) In other words, femicide is a kind of “violence against women” (*Etherington et al., 2015:4*) and the causes of femicide are related with “gender inequality, gender expectations, and systemic gender-based discrimination.” (*Etherington et al., 2015:4*) Another reason of femicide is with the treating the “patriarchal order” (*Iranzo, 2015:1*) such as Turkey is controlled by patriarchal order.

Furthermore, femicide is associated with gender discrimination and at the end of the gender inequality women and girls killed by others. As Helgeson (2017) mentions sex and gender are different terms and sex refers biological categories, such as genes, chromosomes, and hormones. On the other side, gender refers to the social categories (*Helgeson, 2017:30*). In addition, as Helgeson mentions (2017) gender role is a term that based on “society’s influence on the biologically based categories of female and male” (*Helgeson, 2017:31*). It means that gender role is related with a set of norms and expectations of society (*Helgeson, 2017:30*). To rephrase it, gender roles define being male and female (*Helgeson, 2017:31*). Such as women are more emotional and men are strong than women (*Helgeson, 2017:31*). Because of the gender roles masculine and feminine have different features such as traits, behaviours, and interest, which are assigned by society.

The purpose of the study is to analyse the femicide and child marriage cases in Turkey by using the statistical sources to show that femicide and child marriages are one of the big problems of Turkey. The tasks of the study are to finish with the reasons of femicide and child marriages, and offer some solutions to those problems.

Literature Review

As Burr (1998) mentions “Gender is the social significance of sex” (*Burr, 1998:11*). It is the expectations of society for men and women that we call them masculinity and femininity (*Burr, 1998:11*). For example, according to Burr (1998) masculinity is the way of being a man and femininity is the way of being a woman that the expected behaviours and traits of society and culture (*Burr, 1998:146-156*) As Burr summaries (1998) masculinity and femininity are created by people who share the culture because of this they are not stable. They are changeable (*Burr, 1998:12-13*).

Moreover, gender differentiation, which is based on the contradiction of between male and female, and it does not have any relation with biology (*Burr, 1998*) Sex differentiation leads or supports the sex discrimination between male and female. Especially against women (*Burr, 1998:12*). It can be suggested that the reason of gender differences and gender discrimination is patriarchy, which is based on “rule by the father” (*Burr, 1998:14*). In other words, today the term refers “power inequalities between women and men” (*Burr, 2002:14*). From the different perspectives, according to Walby patriarchy is a kind of system and practices of culture that man

has power to control, harass and abuse women (*Walby, 1990:20*).

Furthermore, discrimination is “the consequence of prejudices and make them powerless.” (*Agciban & Gokce, 2018:258*), because the prejudices means one who has gender schematic. Gender Schematic is “about what to wear, how to behave, what career to pursue, what leisure interests to pursue, and what emotions to present to others” (*Helgeson, 2012: 169*) Thus, social biases which are discrimination, stereotype and prejudices are the reasons of femicide and child marriages.

Discrimination, Stereotype and Prejudges

Dovidio, Hewstone, Glick, and Esses (2010) describe three forms of social bias, which are prejudice, stereotypes, and discriminations as:

- a) prejudice, an attitude reflecting an overall evaluation of a group;
- b) stereotypes, associations, and attributions of specific characteristics to a group;
- c) discrimination, biased behaviour toward, and treatment of, a group or its members (*Dovidio et al., 2010:5*).

In 1949, Secretary-General of the United Nations defined discrimination as unequal and adverse treatment leading to inequality between members of the privileged category and non-members, by denying the rights or social advantages of members of a particular social class, or by imposing special conditions on them; or by providing a variety of advantages to members of another category (*The main types and causes of discrimination, 1949*).

In other words, “discrimination is an unequal treatment based on the application of an illegitimate criterion” (*Fassin, 2002:403-423*). In addition, as Ceylan Matbassı mentions low-income individuals have higher discrimination than high-income individuals (*2019:15*).

From the different perspective, according to APA Whereas References:

- prejudices are unfavourable affective reactions to or evaluations of groups and their members,
- stereotypes are generalised beliefs about groups and their members,
- interpersonal discrimination is differential treatment by individuals toward some groups and their members relative to other groups and their members,
- institutional discrimination involves policies and contexts that create, enact, reify, and maintain inequality.

On the other hand, prejudice, stereotypes, and discrimination are pointed different stigmatized groups which are defined by their age, language, gender, religion, ethnicity, race, sexual orientation, and etc. (APA Whereas References) In short, gender discrimination is one of the big problems around the world and in Turkey as well. One of the results of gender inequalities or discrimination is Early Child Marriages.

Early Child Marriages

Early child marriages defined as any kind of formal or informal marriage between children before the age of 18 (*Unicef, 2021*). According to Tahera Ahmed (2015) child marriage common for girls, but concerns to both girls and boys (*Ahmed, 2015:8*). As Polat and Reva (2019) point out that child brides face with different risks such as problems in pregnancy and childbirth,

constricting HIV/AIDS and suffering domestic violence because, physically and emotionally are not ready to become wives and mothers. In addition, according to Polat and Reva (2019) the reasons of the child brides are connected with poverty, education, and economy (Polat, & Reva, 2019:339).

Turkey is one of the countries that face with child marriages especially after education reforms in 2012. The reason is that compulsory education is separated into three four-year periods, and they allow the home schooling. This home-schooling law may be increasing the child brides (Child Marriage in Tukey, 2014:3).

Unicef Turkey states that because of the low socio-economic position, girls in Turkey force to marry before 18 years old and fit themselves into the traditional gender roles. Also, as Unfpa Türkiye states in their report “1 out of every 3 women who got married before the age of 18 became a mother as a child” (I will fight early marriages with all my power, 2022). Accordingly, 19-year-old Helin is trying to save girls from the forced marriage (I will fight early marriages with all my power, 2022).

Another report, which is dated back 5 March 2021 indicates that children who married before 18 are mother and almost half of forced marriage women faced with physical violence. (I will fight early marriages with all my power, 2022) The statistic that took from 2008 till 2020, summarised by Zeynep Dierks (2022) and she mentioned that “child marriage in case of girls totalled around 13 thousand while in case boys the number was way lower, measuring at 726 cases. At the age group of 16 to 17 years old, 0.73 percent of girls and 0.03% of boys got married in 2020 in Turkey.” As the Duvar web page shows that in 2020, 13,740 children married and 95 percent of those marriages belonged to the girls (2021). The Turkish Statistical Institute (2022) 2021 results illustrate that under 18 age females married more than male.

Diagram 1 shows the first marriages under age of 18. Females (24.2%) married under age of 18 more than males (4.4%) and diagram 2 illustrate that percentages of arranged marriage without the opinion of male was 8.6 and female was 12.5.

Table 1 (Turkstat report) describes the range of the early marriages between male and female and the provinces. Between the years of 2011-2021 472,304 males had first marriage between 16-19 and female percentage was 462,317. It means that female had more first marriage than male.

Table 2 indicates that the maximum number of people who married between 16-19 and the name of the provinces in 2021. Between the ages of 16-19 Gaziantep was the first place who had first marriages with the number of 3,612, and Diyarbakır follows with the number of 1918. Those numbers belong to female marriages between 16-19 ages. On the other side, male numbers were 242 at Gaziantep and 229 at Diyarbakır.

According to the report of IMDAT (Violence Prevention and Rehabilitation Association) Turkey was the first country in Europe about the child marriages with the percentage of 2%. (Cumhuriyet Newspaper, 2021). Also, the Cumhuriyet Newspaper mentions the Turkish Statistics Institute report and according to this report (2020) the total marriage number is 487,270 and the girl child marriage number was 13,014. The girl child marriage percentage was 2.7% and boy child marriage percentage was 0.1% (Cumhuriyet Newspaper, 2021).

Moreover, NTV News (2021) remarks the ideas of Gökhan Yıldırım’s thematic analysis of 6 big research and says that it does not have any changes of child married in Turkey in last 10

years. Also, the NTV news point out that still 15 out of 100 children have forced early marriage. Even, 9 out of 10 children who married before 18 said that “they want to marry after 20 (*NTV News, 2021*).

Those statistics and results show that in Turkey most of the girl children married before 18 ages and because of this they faced to gender discrimination.

Femicide

Besides of child marriages, femicide is another big problem of Turkey. Still in this technological age women are not free and they are killed by men in Turkey.

According to the We Will Stop Femicide (Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız) Platform in 2021, 280 women killed. The figure 1 shows the number of killed women according to the province.

Furthermore, the figure 1 displays the Online Monument Counter. He website displays the number (278) and the names of killed women because of the domestic violence.

According to the We Will Stop Femicide Platform (Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu) in May 2022, 35 women killed by men and 16 women’s death found doubtful (2022). On the other hand, again the same platform indicates that in 2021 280 women killed by men and in the same year 217 women’s death found doubtful (2022).

Moreover, the recent report of Stockholm Center for Freedom reported the report of Duvar News and says that “a total of 25 women were murdered in Turkey in March, while 19 women died under suspicious circumstances” (2022).

Literacy Level of Turkey

Table 3 the literacy level of Turkey statistic presents that in 2019 with the 99.08 percentage males’ literacy level is higher than female.

On the other hand, UNESCO (Institute for Statistics) Turkey mentions the illiterate populations and literacy rate of Turkey.

Illiterate Population and Literacy Rate tables (7-8) show us the average of the families’ education level. Uneducated people who are 65 and older may allow forced marriage and as can be seen they are uneducated people.

On the other side, diagram 3 between the years 2020 and 2021 male and female have the close enrolment level of education. As diagram 4 presents the main difference between male and female, who completed at least one education level. In 2020 female percentage is 87.7 and male percentage is 98.1.

Table 6, TurkStat, National Education Statistics Database presents the peoples’ education level that based on sex from 2008 till 2021. The statistics illustrates that illiterate female population is 1,593,893 and male percentage was 268,639. In addition, without a diploma literate female percentage was 4 on 305,606 and male percentage was 3 on 2,246,969. On the other side TurkStat statistic has an interesting result between female and male about schools and educational institutions. For example, below the table summarises the differences between female and male about educational level. Also, as given in the table 6 males are more educated than female in 2021.

Employment Rate

From the different perspective employment rate is another important issue that effects gender discrimination and early child marriages. As shown in diagram 5 female unemployment rate are higher than male. On the other side, male employment rate is higher than female.

Discussion and Reasons of Child Marriages and Femicide

The Guardian Newspaper (*McKernan, 2020*) points out the government ideas about women that “women are not equal to men, and those without children are deficient” and “rather than physically attack women in public wearing shorts, they should verbally harass them instead” (2020) that is the general ideas of government policy.

Another way to say it, in Turkey is connected with the discourses of government policy that is “women and men could not be treated equally. It is against nature,” accusing feminists of “rejecting motherhood” (*Cariou, 2021*).

The rejection of Istanbul Convention (*Interview..., 2022*) is another reason for femicide and the early child marriages. According to government policy the reason of the rejection of Istanbul Convention is against the Turkish family structure/patriarchal structure of Turkey. As they mention “Istanbul Convention ‘threatens family values’ (*Cariou, 2021*).

Education and Literacy tables (9-10) show us the average of the families’ education level. Uneducated people who are 65 and older may allow forced marriage and as can be seen they are uneducated people.

According to Gül Akbal (2021) the reasons of femicide are gender, patriarchal structures, violence, fear and oppression, politics, and authoritarianism. The other is the economic situations of people, who force children to face early child marriage (*Unicef Türkiye*). Traditions and values are another reason of girl brides. They increase the poverty and lack of education can be seen in the analysis part.

COVID-19 pandemic is another reason of femicide, because women had to stay in the abusive situations. They did not have any chance to take help or go outside for help. Also, because of the pandemic women subject to online and offline abuse, harassment, backlash, and threats (Unwomen).

According to Burcu Karakaş (2019) “nationalist and Islamist discourse becomes more dominant and male violence is seen as legitimate, women are becoming easier targets for abuse and violence.” In other words, other reasons are listed by Caroline Warrick (2020) as:

- 1) gender-based and domestic homicides are often referred to as “honor killings”;
- 2) femicide in Turkey is on the rise;
- 3) legal framework has been laid to protect women;
- 4) female empowerment has led to women in Turkey achieving economic independence;
- 5) the Turkish government practically encourages gender-based violence.

Finally, as Daniel Bellut and Burcu Karakaş (2019) mention the ignorance of child marriages and femicide are one of the big problems of Turkey.

Conclusion

All the data that presented show the roles of the women the political and social reforms about women have effected by the dominant ideology of patriarchal family. the because of the

patriarchal family (*Gökçe Demir et al., 2013:150*). As Tuba Kabasakal (2018) mentions violence against women in Turkey is connected with the “culture, societal values and religion” discourses (*Kabasakal, 2018:71*). In short as mentioned before the femicide and early child marriages are consequences of the social biases, which are prejudices, stereotype, and the gender inequality. In addition, still in this Turkey fight with femicide and child marriages, because of the of the illiteracy, economic difficulties, education system, and political or government policies.

Furthermore, the analysis shows that early child marriages and femicide have close relation with the education level of people because “as educational status of people increased, the proportion of marriages with people's own decision increased and the proportion of arranged marriages decreased” (*Turkstat, 2022*). It means that uneducated has potentiality to support femicide and early child marriages.

So, as Cumhuriyet Newspaper (2021) Newspaper points out that in general society does not have enough knowledge and awareness about child marriage, and because of this they do not know where they can apply when they face with child marriage. (*Cumhuriyet Newspaper, 2021*).

Consequently, as Ecevit mentions “Gender is not stable, it is fiction and changeable”. (*Ecevit, 2021:11*).

Solutions

Solutions of the femicide and child marriages could be listed as follow:

- Law Regulations,
- Changes of discourses and government policies,
- Education levels,
- To search and apply the world strategies and apply them,
- Literacy Levels,
- Improve the traditional and cultural values,
- To enhance awareness levels.

References:

- Agcihan, E., & Gokce, A.T. (2018). Analyzing the Types of Discrimination in Turkish for Foreigners Books. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 6(2), 257-264. DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2018.060207
- Ahmed, T. (2015). Child Marriage: A Discussion Paper. *Bangladesh Journal of Bioethics*, 6(2), 8-14.
- Akbal, G. (2021). *Femicides in Turkey: Understanding Femicides through the Social, Political, and Gendered Context* (Dissertation). Retrieved July 10, 2022, from <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:liu:diva-178714>
- APA Whereas References. *APA Resolution on Prejudice, Stereotypes, and Discrimination*. Retrieved June 8, 2022, from <https://www.apa.org/about/policy/prejudice.pdf>
- Bellut, D., & Karakas, B. (2019, December 9). Femicides in Turkey: A problem that is being ignored. Retrieved July 2, 2022, from <https://www.dw.com/en/femicides-in-turkey-a-problem-that-is-being-ignored/a-51587652>

- Burr, V. (1998). *Gender and Social Psychology. Psychology Focus*. Routledge: London and New York.
- Cariou, L. (2021). Gender-Based Violence in Turkey on The Rise: The Government Is to Blame. In: Equal Rights, Politics & Foreign Affairs. Retrieved July 20, 2022, from <https://impakter.com/gender-based-violence-in-turkey-on-the-rise-the-government-is-to-blame/>
- Child Marriage (2021). Unicef for every child. Retrieved June 12, 2022, from <https://www.unicef.org/protection/child-marriage>
- Child Marriage (2021). Unicef Turkey for every child. Retrieved August 1, 2022, from <https://www.unicef.org/turkiye/en/child-marriage>
- Child Marriage in Tukey (Overview) (2014). United nations Population Fund (UNFPA). Retrieved August 5, 2022, from <https://eeca.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/unfpa%20turkey%20overview.pdf>
- Cumhuriyet Newspaper. (2021, April 30). Türkiye çocuk yaşta evliliklerde Avrupa birincisi. Retrieved August 3, 2022, from <https://www.cumhuriyet.com.tr/haber/turkiye-cocuk-yasta-evliliklerde-avrupa-birincisi-1832341> (in Turkish)
- Dağ, H., Yetim, A., Ketenci, A.Ö., & Hançerli, T.S. (2021). A Child Abuse: Marriage at childhood age. *Türk Arch Pediatr*, 56(6), 548-552.
- Demir, A., G., Bulucu, D., G., & Özcan, A. (2013). Men's View Towards Violence Against Women. *Balıkesir Sağlık Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2, 3.
- Dierks, Z. (2022, February 7). Number of registered child marriages in Turkey 2008-2020. Retrieved May 28, 2022, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1288377/number-of-registered-child-marriages-in-turkey>
- Dovidio, J.F., Hewstone, M., Glick, P., & Esses, V.M. (2010) Prejudice, Stereotyping and Discrimination: Theoretical and Empirical Overview. *The SAGE Handbook of Prejudice, Stereotyping and Discrimination*, 3-28. DOI: 10.4135/9781446200919.N1.
- DuvaR.english (2021, April 23). More than 13,00 children married off in turkey in 2020. Retrieved July 10, 2022, from <https://www.duvarenglish.com/more-than-13000-children-married-off-in-turkey-in-2020-news-57210>
- Education, Culture, Sport and Tourism (2022). Turkish Statistical Institute. Retrieved June 1, 2022, from <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Kategori/GetKategori?p=Education,-Culture,-Sport-and-Tourism-105>
- Ecevit, Y. (2021). *Toplumsal Cinsiyet Eşitliğinin Temel Kavramları. Eğitim Materyali*. Toplumsal Cinsiyet Eşitliğinin İzlenemsi Projesi.
- Etherington, N., Baker, L., Pietsche, N., Straatman, A.L., Ansems, A., Barreto, E., & Campbell, M. (2015). Femicide. *Centre for Research & Education on Violence Against Women & Children. Learning Network*, 14, 1-8. Retrieved July 28, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280310173_Femicide
- Fassin, D. (2002). L'invention Française de La Discrimination. *Revue Française de Science Politique*, 4(52), 403-423. (in French)
- Helgeson, S.V. (2017) *Psychology of Gender*. 5th Edition. Routledge: New York and London.
- I will fight early marriages with all my power (2022, January 14). UNFPA Türkiye. Retrieved June 12, 2022, from <https://turkiye.unfpa.org/en/news/i-will-fight-early-marriages-all-my-power>

- Interview: How Turkey's Failure to Protect Women Can Cost Them Their Lives: Authorities Need To Act To Prevent Femicides (2022, May 26). Retrieved May 28, 2022, from <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/05/26/interview-how-turkeys-failure-protect-women-can-cost-them-their-lives>
- Kabasakal, T. (2018) *Violence Against Women in Turkey: An Analysis of Barriers to the Effective Implementation of International Commitments*. Master Thesis. Faculty of Law. Lund University. Retrieved July 18, 2022, from <https://lup.lub.lu.se/luur/download?func=downloadFile&recordOID=8955271&fileOID=8955273>
- Karakaş, B. (2019, December 18). Femicide in Turkey: What's lacking is political will. Retrieved July 3, 2022, from <https://www.mei.edu/publications/femicide-turkey-whats-lacking-political-will>
- Institute for Statistics (UNESCO). Education and Literacy. Retrieved August 8, 2022, from <http://uis.unesco.org/en/country/tr>
- Iranzo, J.M. (2015) 'Reflections on femicide and violence against women'. *Working paper on femicide (unpublished)*. Universidad de Zaragoza: GESES.
- Kouta, C., Rousou, E., Freysteinsdóttir, F.J., Boira, S., & Naudi, M. (2017). Gender and Socio-Cultural Perspectives through Femicide Case Studied. *Journal of Community Medicine & Health Care*, 2(2), 1013.
- Labour Force Statistics (2022, August 10). Turkish Statistical Institute. Retrieved August 11, 2022, from <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Labour-Force-Statistics-June-2022-45651&dil=2>
- Matbasi, C. (2019). *The Perception of Discrimination*. İstanbul.
- McKernan, B. (2020, July 23). The Guardian. Murder in Turkey sparks outrage over rising violence against women. Retrieved July 8, 2022, from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/jul/23/turkey-outrage-rising-violence-against-women>
- NTV Haber (2021, March 5). Türkiye'de çocuk gelin raporu: 100 çocuktan 15'i çocuk yaşta evlendirildi. Retrieved June 15, 2022, from <https://www.ntv.com.tr/turkiye/turkiyede-cocuk-gelin-raporu-100-cocuktan-15i-cocuk-yasta-evlendirildi,uVkBex8yxUuICLLSfLgh8A> (in Turkish)
- O'Neill, A., (2022, February 16). Literacy Rate in Turkey 2019. Retrieved June 15, 2022, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/575187/literacy-rate-in-turkey/#professional>
- Oakley, A. (1972). *Sex, Gender and Society*. Gower/Maurice Temple Smith, New Society Series. Editor Paul Barker.
- Polat, O., & Reva, Z., (2019). Forced marriages as human rights violation. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Education Research*, 1(5), 339.
- Stockholm Center for Freedom. (2022). 25 women in Turkey victims of femicide in March. Retrieved August 8, 2022, from <https://stockholmcf.org/25-women-in-turkey-victims-of-femicide-in-march/>
- Şiddeten Ölen Kadınlar İçin Dijital Anıt (The Monument Counter) (2022). Retrieved August 18, 2022, from <http://anitsayac.com/> (in Turkish)
- The Last 25 years of child marriages in Turkey (2021, March 5). UNFPA Türkiye. Retrieved June

- 12, 2022, from <https://turkiye.unfpa.org/en/news/last-25-years-child-marriages-turkey>
- The main types and causes of discrimination (Memorandum submitted by the Secretary-General) (1945). United Nations Digital Library. Retrieved July 10, 2022, from https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/1638125/files/E_CN-4_Sub-2_40_Rev-1-EN.pdf
- Toplumsal Cinsiyet İstatistikleri: Gender Statistics 2021 (2022). Türkiye Statistik Kurumu. Turkish Statistical Institute. Retrieved July 10, 2022, from https://www.tuik.gov.tr/media/announcements/toplumsal_cinsiyet_istatistikleri_2021.pdf
- Türkiye Family Structure Survey, 2021 (2022, April 1). Turkish Statistical Institute. Retrieved June 6, 2022, from <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Turkiye-Family-Structure-Survey-2021-45813&dil=2>
- Gender-Based Violence: Women and girls at risk (2022). Unwomen. Retrieved July 19, 2022, from https://www.unwomen.org/en/hq-complex-page/covid-19-rebuilding-for-resilience/gender-based-violence?gclid=Cj0KCQjwidSWBhDdARIsAIoTVb0tjibUHAjmrX8pdmz_9lwtHPqoZjAGwiwFLUNXo2wvmJkawaVIRU8aAiplEALw_wcB
- Walby, S. (1990) *Theorizing Patriarchy*, Oxford: Blackwell.
- Warrick, C. (2020, September 3). 5 Facts about Femicide in Turkey. Retrieved July 10, 2022, from <https://borgenproject.org/femicide-in-turkey/>
- We Will Stop Femicide Platform (Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu) (2021). Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu 2021 Yıllık Veri Raporu. Retrieved July 10, 2022, from <https://kadincinayetleriniurduracagiz.net/veriler/3003/kadin-cinayetlerini-durduracagiz-platformu-2021-yillik-veri-raporu>
- We Will Stop Femicide Platform (Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu) (2022). Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu 2021 Yıllık Veri Raporu. Retrieved August 10, 2022, from <https://kadincinayetleriniurduracagiz.net/veriler/3021/kadin-cinayetlerini-durduracagiz-platformu-mayis-2022-raporu>
- Women in Statistics, 2021 (2022, March 4). Turkish Statistical Institute. Retrieved June 15, 2022, from <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Istatistiklerle-Kadin-2021-45635&dil=2#:~:text=When%20the%20proportion%20of%20those,%25%20and%2098.1%25%20in%202020>
- Youth in Statistics, 2021 (2022). Turkish Statistical Institute. Retrieved July 1, 2022, from <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Istatistiklerle-Genclik-2021-45634>

Appendix

Diagram 1. Age at first marriage by sex, 2021 (*Türkiye Family Structure Survey..., 2022*)

Diagram 2. Decision of marriage by sex, 2021 (*Türkiye Family Structure Survey..., 2022*)

Diagram 3. Net enrolment rate by level of education and sex, 2020/'2. (*Youth in Statistics..., 2022*)

Diagram 4. Proportion of those who have completed at least one educational level by sex (%), 2008-2020. (*Women in Statistics...*, 2022).

Diagram 5. Unemployment and Employment Rates (June 2020-June 2022). (*Labour Force Statistics, 2022*)

Unemployment rate, June 2020-June 2022

Employment rate, June 2020-June 2022

Table 1. Spouses at first marriages by age group, 2011-2021 (*Toplumsal Cinsiyet İstatistikleri...*, 2022)

5.1 Yaş grubuna göre ilk defa evlenenler, 2011-2021											
Spouses at first marriages by age group, 2011-2021											
Yaş grubu	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020 ^(r)	2021
Age group											
Erkek-Male											
Toplam	509 739	515 198	513 728	512 612	514 329	503 480	483 501	467 882	455 965	407 663	472 304
Total	509 739	515 198	513 728	512 612	514 329	503 480	483 501	467 882	455 965	407 663	472 304
16-19	14 203	14 189	13 532	12 603	11 641	10 955	9 805	9 291	8 367	6 915	6 857
20-24	160 772	158 578	154 091	151 530	148 415	143 148	134 191	125 516	116 972	104 689	114 891
25-29	229 455	231 029	232 504	230 856	232 337	226 736	219 078	212 611	210 826	188 441	219 124
30-34	81 494	85 431	86 218	88 397	90 237	88 387	86 138	85 644	85 011	76 226	93 080
35-39	17 410	18 984	20 236	21 445	23 418	25 296	25 199	25 395	24 987	22 147	26 980
40-44	4 119	4 599	4 878	5 437	5 776	6 225	6 312	6 543	6 875	6 590	8 145
45-49	1 462	1 474	1 413	1 507	1 594	1 709	1 793	1 867	1 896	1 736	2 132
50+	824	914	855	837	911	1 024	985	1 015	1 031	919	1 095
Bilinmeyen											
Unknown	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Kadın - Female											
Toplam	514 423	520 069	516 635	513 238	512 234	497 722	477 408	459 812	447 055	399 237	462 317
Total	514 423	520 069	516 635	513 238	512 234	497 722	477 408	459 812	447 055	399 237	462 317
16-19	130 129	128 550	122 537	115 660	107 665	98 933	88 739	81 647	71 177	58 413	57 770
20-24	207 432	208 275	205 595	205 527	205 720	200 386	192 214	184 144	177 698	160 508	182 111
25-29	123 432	125 961	131 141	133 205	138 994	138 728	138 829	137 528	142 053	129 855	160 090
30-34	35 940	38 309	38 076	38 564	38 498	37 408	35 852	35 267	35 505	32 153	41 078
35-39	10 860	11 436	11 729	12 101	12 979	13 884	13 151	12 728	12 032	10 309	11 976
40-44	3 700	4 234	4 493	4 947	5 094	5 018	5 164	4 867	4 921	4 595	5 293
45-49	1 819	1 956	1 798	1 871	1 866	1 922	2 037	2 185	2 198	2 053	2 328
50+	1 111	1 347	1 265	1 363	1 418	1 443	1 422	1 446	1 471	1 351	1 671
Bilinmeyen											
Unknown	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TÜİK, Toplumsal Cinsiyet İstatistikleri, 2021						TurkStat, Gender Statistics, 2021					
Kaynak: Evlenme İstatistikleri, 2011-2021						Source: Marriage Statistics, 2011-2021					
(r) Evlenme verileri güncel idari kayıtlarla revize edilmiştir.						(r) Marriage data were revised with updated administrative records.					
- Bilgi yoktur.						- Denotes magnitude null.					

Table 2. Marriages by province and age group, 2021 (*Toplumsal Cinsiyet İstatistikleri... , 2022*)

Marriage														Evllenme		
5.3 İllere ve yaş grubuna göre evlenenler, 2021																
Marriages by province and age group, 2021																
[Olay yerine göre-By the place of event]																
İl Province	Cinsiyet Sex	Toplam Total	Yaş grubu-Age group												Bilinmeyen Unknown	
			16-19	20-24	25-29	30-34	35-39	40-44	45-49	50-54	55-59	60-64	65-69	70-74		75+
Toplam-Total	Erkek-Male	561 710	6 920	116 610	226 899	107 109	43 014	23 128	13 008	8 433	6 443	4 189	2 943	1 642	1 372	-
	Kadın-Female	561 710	59 661	191 966	177 690	60 262	29 517	18 631	11 098	6 069	3 723	1 818	830	322	120	3
Adana	Erkek-Male	15 573	175	3 354	6 059	3 023	1 185	647	368	226	218	147	103	35	33	-
	Kadın-Female	15 573	1 783	5 420	4 631	1 693	808	563	291	173	115	57	28	8	2	1
Adıyaman	Erkek-Male	5 055	40	1 006	2 293	1 054	291	147	71	41	37	22	23	18	12	-
	Kadın-Female	5 055	663	1 977	1 543	460	181	97	69	30	21	10	1	1	2	-
Afyonkarahisar	Erkek-Male	5 267	133	1 739	1 940	719	303	145	83	61	62	27	26	14	15	-
	Kadın-Female	5 267	887	2 185	1 278	378	199	141	93	52	30	13	5	6	-	-
Ağrı	Erkek-Male	3 833	58	1 258	1 719	550	131	41	28	13	18	2	8	5	2	-
	Kadın-Female	3 833	1 320	1 508	699	175	58	33	19	9	6	2	1	1	1	1
Amasya	Erkek-Male	2 017	14	383	878	380	156	65	38	37	19	15	17	4	11	-
	Kadın-Female	2 017	156	737	658	215	99	59	34	30	16	7	2	4	-	-
Ankara	Erkek-Male	34 770	231	5 699	14 309	7 310	2 969	1 670	873	631	464	277	176	90	71	-
	Kadın-Female	34 770	2 174	10 272	12 673	4 586	2 135	1 252	748	443	274	125	61	19	7	1
Antalya	Erkek-Male	16 977	180	2 855	6 212	3 229	1 683	989	635	451	307	189	136	61	50	-
	Kadın-Female	16 977	1 179	5 035	5 307	2 132	1 242	870	571	313	181	90	34	18	5	-
Artvin	Erkek-Male	953	8	92	370	244	109	52	28	20	9	6	7	4	4	-
	Kadın-Female	953	47	238	396	132	56	31	25	11	11	4	2	-	-	-
Aydın	Erkek-Male	7 795	98	1 419	2 811	1 505	692	432	256	178	144	125	72	41	22	-
	Kadın-Female	7 795	778	2 310	2 314	923	536	354	258	142	100	49	25	5	1	-
Balıkesir	Erkek-Male	8 129	128	1 561	3 155	1 464	598	397	251	180	144	110	75	30	36	-
	Kadın-Female	8 129	742	2 661	2 499	874	460	336	220	152	95	53	25	8	4	-
Bilecik	Erkek-Male	1 357	12	269	559	268	101	60	24	29	16	9	4	4	2	-
	Kadın-Female	1 357	98	521	430	138	66	46	32	14	5	4	2	1	-	-
Bingöl	Erkek-Male	1 823	15	313	777	423	148	60	29	16	18	9	5	5	5	-
	Kadın-Female	1 823	185	662	597	206	69	45	38	11	2	7	-	-	1	-
Bitlis	Erkek-Male	2 421	23	642	1 117	445	108	38	14	8	9	9	4	3	1	-
	Kadın-Female	2 421	594	1 010	577	145	48	22	10	5	5	2	2	-	1	-
Bolu	Erkek-Male	1 828	14	346	774	352	155	86	37	18	11	16	10	6	3	-
	Kadın-Female	1 828	107	613	648	226	107	57	41	12	8	6	2	-	1	-
Burdur	Erkek-Male	1 770	30	406	710	274	130	77	43	34	18	19	13	9	7	-
	Kadın-Female	1 770	224	652	496	156	86	64	38	21	18	10	3	1	1	-
Bursa	Erkek-Male	20 119	197	3 565	8 589	3 892	1 575	910	502	331	238	136	98	45	41	-
	Kadın-Female	20 119	1 457	6 882	6 915	2 155	1 085	753	429	205	128	69	24	15	2	-
Çanakkale	Erkek-Male	3 367	46	533	1 256	701	308	170	104	99	59	48	24	16	3	-
	Kadın-Female	3 367	261	1 010	1 098	397	213	165	104	59	30	18	11	1	-	-
Çankırı	Erkek-Male	1 069	12	307	423	167	53	35	23	11	11	10	6	5	6	-
	Kadın-Female	1 069	135	455	292	67	41	31	18	10	11	5	2	2	-	-
Çorum	Erkek-Male	3 545	27	837	1 402	637	252	112	68	52	53	29	24	29	23	-
	Kadın-Female	3 545	352	1 326	1 082	321	155	110	71	52	46	16	8	5	1	-
Denizli	Erkek-Male	7 538	92	1 463	2 951	1 401	667	370	190	130	110	60	56	23	25	-
	Kadın-Female	7 538	658	2 505	2 402	826	432	323	167	98	59	47	17	4	-	-
Diyarbakır	Erkek-Male	11 714	229	3 064	4 782	2 313	688	270	119	63	84	32	36	19	15	-
	Kadın-Female	11 714	1 918	4 442	3 313	1 171	443	221	117	45	29	7	7	-	1	-
Edirne	Erkek-Male	2 320	75	454	828	459	202	120	63	51	26	19	15	5	3	-
	Kadın-Female	2 320	318	639	720	271	152	94	66	28	16	10	6	-	-	-
Elazığ	Erkek-Male	4 035	31	757	1 720	847	304	164	79	46	46	14	18	3	6	-
	Kadın-Female	4 035	267	1 484	1 414	403	204	136	66	29	21	8	-	2	1	-
Erzincan	Erkek-Male	1 309	11	217	627	232	106	44	27	16	9	8	5	2	5	-
	Kadın-Female	1 309	103	473	471	130	45	39	17	16	8	5	-	2	-	-
Erzurum	Erkek-Male	4 694	72	982	2 147	944	283	95	61	24	35	21	12	13	5	-
	Kadın-Female	4 694	688	1 785	1 539	369	123	77	49	27	21	7	6	2	1	-
Eskişehir	Erkek-Male	5 602	65	890	2 158	1 230	550	275	153	103	74	53	26	16	9	-
	Kadın-Female	5 602	325	1 589	2 053	765	364	205	141	82	49	18	7	3	1	-
Gaziantep	Erkek-Male	16 823	242	5 500	6 690	2 370	820	422	233	147	137	100	77	51	34	-
	Kadın-Female	16 823	3 612	6 976	3 807	1 103	521	372	206	99	77	29	14	3	4	-

TÜİK, Toplumsal Cinsiyet İstatistikleri, 2021

Kaynak: TÜİK, Evlenme İstatistikleri, 2021

- Bilgi yoktur.

TurkStat, Gender Statistics, 2021

Source: TurkStat, Marriage Statistics, 2021

- Denotes magnitude null.

Table 3. The Literacy Rate in Turkey 2019 (O'Neill, 2022)

Turkey: Literacy rate from 2007 to 2019, total and by gender

Characteristic	Adult total	Adult male	Adult female
2019	96.74%	99.08%	94.42%
2017	96.15%	98.82%	93.5%
2016	96.17%	98.78%	93.56%
2015	95.6%	98.58%	92.65%
2014	95.44%	98.5%	92.4%
2013	95.26%	98.4%	92.14%
2012	94.92%	98.26%	91.6%
2011	94.11%	97.94%	90.31%
2010	92.66%	97.3%	88.07%
2009	90.82%	96.38%	85.35%
2007	88.66%	96.2%	81.26%

Showing entries 1 to 11 (11 entries in total)

© Statista 2022

Table 4. Illiterate Population (Institute for Statistics, 2022)

	TOTAL	MALE	FEMALE	
Illiterate population				
15-24 years	12,599	2,473	10,126	(2019)
15 years and older	2,088,846	284,914	1,803,932	(2019)

Table 5. Literacy Rate (Institute for Statistics, 2022)

	TOTAL	MALE	FEMALE	
Literacy rate (%)				
15-24 years	99.9	100	99.8	(2019)
15 years and older	96.7	99.1	94.4	(2019)
65 years and older	83.1	94.6	74	(2019)

Table 6. Schools and Educational Institutions by Gender (*Education, Culture, Sport and Tourism, 2022*)

2021	General Total	Illiterate	Literate without a diploma	Primary School	Primary Education	Lower Secondary School	Upper Secondary School	Universities and other higher educational Ins.	Master	Doctorate
Female	37,877,223	1,593,893	4,305,606	9,610,023	2,232,443	6,204,007	7,248,883	5,550,811	638,869	96,774
Male	37,879,709	268,639	3,224,669	7,267,940	2,899,977	7,434,209	9,448,709	6,086,476	756,363	136,568

Figure 1. Monument Counter (*Şiddeten Ölen Kadınlar İçin Dijital Anıt, 2022*)

ŞİDDETEN ÖLEN KADINLAR İÇİN DİJİTAL ANIT

AÇIKLAMA ENGLISH

Arama

2022 2021 2020 2019 2018 2017 2016 2015 2014 2013 2012 2011 2010 2009 2008

Dilek Karaman | Arzu Ar | Arzi Elen | Sunay Aslan Kaya | Fadime Cuma | Necla Aydođdu | Şermin Sarı | Sultan Karaaslan | Sevtap Akbaci | Leyla Karaaslan | Derya Karaaslan | Melek Karaaslan | Şerife Karaaslan | Firdavs Babat | İsmi Bilinmiyor | İsmi Bilinmiyor | Ayşen Çöl | Gülten İnan | Berivan Ustü | Filiz Girgin | Sibel Uyanık | Şenay Ayyaçođlu | Neriman Güngör | Ülkü Akın | Asihaan Sinem Çiçek | Mihriban Arduç | Hanife Çakıcı | Ezgi Zerkın | Ayşe Korur | Hacer Alkan | Dilek Karci | Susenber Özdemir | Beyza Dođan | Mehika Merici | Kader Keskin | Fadim Süner | Hadel Alhadad | Ayşe Polat | Melek Yıldırım | Zehra Bayır | Elif Güneş | Güllü Sülük | Yasemin Demir | Derya Tekin | Birgül Göksu | Elif Gölveren | Yasemin Çedik | Nuriye Mert | Sofia Olifrenko | Pınar Damar | Çađla Alara Pınarci | Ayşecik Dađistanlı Ceylan | Kader Deđirmen | Beste Koçak | Döndü Salman | Emine Yalçın | Zeynep Turgut | Nedime Dinçer | Nobar Gařarova | Sojida Kalandarova | Keziban Demir | N.Ö. | Nurten Orak | Esra Yamaık | Nurgül Gürsoy Dilek | Saliha Birincubur | Nurray Orak | Esra Orak | Esra Altınkaynak | Ngün Söken | Dian Eylem Öz | Ummuhan Yurtseven | Şengül Kaya | Leyla Aksu | Nefise M. | Kübra Ađar | H.G. | Hasbiko Güngör | Yasemin Öztürk | Nazlı Erva Öztürk | Rabia Yılmaz | Nazlı Evra Öztürk | Rabia Aydınlı | Sevim Özdemir | Keremet Nyshanova | Nurten Demirbađ | Yonca Türkman | Hatice Barış | Sorcan Köseođlu | Duru Sila Alpaz | Selin Alpaz | Cansu Sezer | Emine El Ali | Selda Mutlı | Beynan Su Mutlı | Elif Akilli | Havva Ceylan | Emel Evbakan | Garme Akçam | Stalina Luisa | Kazban Sakcak | Suna Bingöl | Özlem Dursun | Yildiz Yazıcı | Merem Köpek | Funda Göđlü | İrem Evren | Hasibe Akbaş | Hatice Birsen | Aysel Bozkurt | Bahiřsor Erdođan | Ezgi Tařiran | Güler Karalı | Saadet Polat | Türkcan Demir | Rojda Şayia | Keziban Bařak Demir | Beril Yarci | Nevriye Şeker | T.N. | Derya Kayra | Gol Bib Sultanı | Merem Sultanı | Merveh Sultanı | D.K. | Rabia Yaman | Cemre Bilmaz | Pınar Kızıl | Şeyma Biran | Handan Uyarođlu | Cansu Aydođdu | Şule Akdeniz Tartık | Tetraana Navrotsky | Sorap Bor | Zehra Çiçek | Nurel Türkmen | Yeliz Kalkan | Lütfiye Ş. | Sinem Sönmez | Safiye Mutlu | Sinem Sökmen | Z.M. | Sakine Kültür | Hatice Çalı | Ayla Kartal | Hülya Ekoca | Sema Kılıç | Salma Kılıç | Aşya Nur Atalay | Sultan İrmak | Garibe Dađ | Nayime Dađ | Zeynep Koyun | Reza M. | Dilek Ceylan | Ayşe Alkan | Ayşe Sevimli | Hatice Ester | Sevgi Yılmaz | Ülkü Dumaz | Berivan Altürk | Fatma Narmann | Sema Tokat | Nur Erdem | Turana Umayeva | Demet Arslan | Fatma Köçük | Ramziye Töysüz | İrem Kostakođlu | Hanım Kařmaz | Öznur Temiz | Elif Göbelek | Ceylan Kılıç | Nurcan Seçer | Emine Caba | Gözde Çelen | Yasemin El Salih | Zeynep Gücük | Duriye G. | Şükriye Gül | Esmâ Sedan | Zerrif Dođan | Gülay Dođan | Bilge Akça | Hatice Karataş | Ayşe Perçem | Gülşen Onat | Esmâ Bal | Şeyma Demir | Ayşe İşlek | Tuba Kızıođlu | Aynur Karayün | Eda Evli | Fadime Koca | Fatma Solak | Nurray Demir | Ece Kılıřaslan Acar | Yađmur Sönmez | Buket Pala | Özge Binnur Oruç